

THE ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYETHERSULPHONE COMPOSITES

Li Ming

Department of Materials Science and Engineering
Tsinghua University, Beijing, China

ABSTRACT

The water absorption properties of T300 carbon fiber reinforced polyethersulphone (PES) composites immersed in water have been investigated. The effects of hygrothermal and thermal ageing on the mechanical properties of T300/PES composites have been discussed. The results showed that the diffusion of water in the composites obeys Fick's law. The mechanical properties of the composites fell down in exponent as the immersing time was prolonged. Heat-treatment at 200°C resulted in some increases of the mechanical properties of composites at elevated temperature.

Keywords: Thermoplastic composites, Water absorption, Hygrothermal ageing, Mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Water absorption and its effects on the mechanical properties of fiber composites are an important subject all along, because water absorption leads not only to a gain in weight and change in dimensions, but also loss in mechanical properties. A great deal of researches about these have been focused on structural composites based on thermosetting matrixes [1-3], for example, epoxy resins. In recent decade, Advanced Thermoplastic Composites (ACTP) based on thermoplastic matrixes such as PEEK, PES, PPS, PEI, PAI and so on, have made a great progress, due to their advantages over those thermosetting composites [4]. Some of them, for example, CF/PEEK and CF/PES have been used for aircraft and other structures [5,6]. Although it is recognized that heat and wet effects on the performance of ACTP are equally as important as thermosetting composites, few data are available for hygrothermal ageing of ACTP. Wang and Springer [7] reported the data for moisture absorption and diffusivity of APC-2 composites exposed to humid air, and for the effect of moisture content on the fracture toughness. Recently, effects of water absorption on the mechanical properties of CF/PPS and CF/PEEK were reported [8]. In present paper, hygrothermal and thermal ageing and their effects on the mechanical properties of CF/PES have been researched and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS

The fibers used was T300-6000B-40B (produced by Toray Co.). PES was supplied by Jilin University. The preregs of T300/PES composites were fabricated by solvent-impregnation technique. Unidirectional laminates were manufactured in plate form by hot-press moulding. The detailed procedure was described in reference [9]. The laminates with lower fiber content were prepared by film stacking method, in which PES film and unidirectional preregs were alternately laid. The dimensions of coupons were 30x20x2mm for water absorption tests, 60x10x2mm for flexure tests and 15x6.5x2mm for short-beam shear tests.

TESTS ON WATER ABSORPTION

After dried in an oven at 150°C for 6 hours, the coupons were shifted into a desiccator to cold down to ambient temperature, and weighted. Then the coupons were immersed in water with constant temperature. After given time, the coupons were drawn out and water upon the surface were immediately cleaned off and weighted.

TESTS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Using a universal materials tester, mechanical properties of the samples were tested at room temperature or elevated temperature. The span was 50mm for flexure, and 10mm for short-beam shear. The speed of cross-head was 2mm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

WATER ABSORPTION

Figure 1 shows four groups of water absorption curves from the water immersion experiments at 28, 50, 75 and 97°C. The each data point in the curves is a average of three experimental results. In all case, PES matrix and the composite laminates with fiber volume content of 22.3%, 32.6% and 58.6% obeyed Fick's law. The linear relationship between water absorption and square root of immersion time appeared in the initial immersion period. The saturation water gains, M_s , increase with increase of immersion temperature and with decrease of fiber content.

A composite laminate absorbs water by four parts, which are matrix, fiber, interface and void. Generally, the water absorption by carbon fiber is much lower than that by matrix. If it is assumed that the composites are free-void and there is no additional water absorbed by interface, a simple equation is obtained:

$$M_s = M_p \cdot W_p \quad \text{or} \quad M_s = M_p \cdot (1 - W_f) \quad (1)$$

Where, M_p is saturation absorption of polymer matrix, W_p and W_f are weight fraction of matrix and fiber respectively. According to above equation, water gain of composites with known fiber content can be calculated. The experimental and calculated results are listed in table 1.

Fig.1 Water absorption curves of CF/PES composites immersed in water. Fiber volume content: (a) 0, (b) 22.3%, (c) 32.6% and (d) 58.6%.

Table 1. Data for Saturation Water Absorption of T300/PES Composites

Sample	V _f (%)	28°C		50°C		75°C		97°C	
		exp.	cal.	exp.	cal.	exp.	cal.	exp.	cal.
PES	0	1.60		1.64		1.70		1.90	
S-1	22.3	1.15	1.17	1.18	1.20	1.23	1.25	1.38	1.39
S-2	32.6	0.95	0.99	0.97	1.02	1.05	1.05	1.14	1.18
S-3	58.6	0.56	0.57	0.58	0.59	0.68	0.61	0.74	0.68

For S-1 and S-2, the experimental data of saturation water absorption are slightly lower than those calculated, which may be attributed to insufficient immersion time in which the laminates do not achieve real water saturation. For S-3, however, M_s tested at 75°C and 97°C is more than ones calculated, which is probably because water absorbed by void or interface can not be ignored.

From the slope *m* of the linear section of water absorption curves (figure 1), diffusivities *D* are obtained by using equation (2):

$$D = \pi h^2 m^2 / 16 M^2 s \tag{2}$$

where h is the thickness of specimens. The Diffusivities D decrease with the increase of fiber content and the drop of temperature. Figure 2 shows a relationship between the diffusivities and the square root of fiber volume fraction. They are well in accord with the relation (3):

$$D_c = D_p(1 - a\sqrt{V_f}) \tag{3}$$

In this paper, a is 1.02 for 28, 50 and 75°C, and 1.05 for 97°C. D_c and D_p refer to the diffusivities of composites and polymer matrix, respectively.

Diffusivities of neat PES and its composites as a function of temperature are shown in figure 3. The linear relation between $\ln D$ and inverse temperature $1/T$ indicates that the diffusivities fit Arrhenius equation (4):

$$D = D_0 \exp(-E_d/RT) \tag{4}$$

Where D_0 is constant, T is absolute temperature (K), E_d is activation energy for diffusion (J/mol•K), $R = 8.314$ J/mol. E_d values evaluated from $\ln D - 1/T$ lines are listed in table 2. E_d decreases with increase of the fiber volume fraction. This indicates water diffusing in the composites needs relatively small energy. It is reasonable that there exists a interface layer (interphase) in the composites and water diffusing in the layer is easier than that in neat matrix.

Fig.2 Diffusivities versus square root of fiber volume content at different water temperature

Fig.3 Diffusivities vs inverse temperature.

Table 2. Activation Energy for Diffusion

Specimen	PES	S-1	S-2	S-3
E_d (KJ/mol)	34.7	34.1	33.5	32.4

HYGROTHERMAL AGEING

Figure 4 and 5 show the short-beam shear strength τ_s and flexural strength σ_f and modulus E_f as the functions of immersing time. In boiling water, σ_f and τ_s sharply fall off during the initial immersing period, and then slow down and approach the limit value $\sigma_f(\infty)$ or $\tau_s(\infty)$. This trend reduces rapidly as the temperature is lowered.

Fig.4 Short-beam shear strengths as functions of immersing time at different water temperature.

Fig.5 Flexure strengths and modulus as functions of immersing time at 97°C

The hydrothermal ageing of composites is a dynamic process. The response of composites on the environments may be expressed in equation (5):

$$\phi = \exp(-t^b/\tau) \quad (5)$$

Where ϕ is a accumulated damage function, t is exposing time to environments, b is a time exponent, and τ is relaxation time. Equation (5) is specialized into equation (6) to express the relation between short-beam shear strength τ_s and immersing time:

$$[\tau_s(t) - \tau_s(\infty)] / [\tau_s(0) - \tau_s(\infty)] = \exp(-t^b/\tau) \quad (6)$$

Where, $\tau_s(0)$, $\tau_s(t)$ and $\tau_s(\infty)$ are the short-beam shear strengths of composites in dry condition, immersed in water for t hours and reaching the ageing limit, respectively. Figure 6 indicates a linear relation between $\ln\{-\ln[(\tau_s(t) - \tau_s(\infty)) / (\tau_s(0) - \tau_s(\infty))]\}$ versus $\ln t$ at 97°C and 75°C. Equation (6) is also suited to flexure strengths, so long as σ_f replaces τ_s . Experimental data are listed in table 3. Same b exponent (0.672) indicates the hydrothermal ageing mechanisms of the composites in varying temperature are identical.

THERMAL AGEING

After the composites are treated at 200°C, the mechanical properties of them at ambient temperature have no obvious changes, as it is indicated in figure 7. It is noted, a small the increase of τ_s occurs for the specimens treated for 12 hours. The mechanical properties of the heat-treated composites at elevated temperature are obviously enhanced, as showed in figure 8. Specially at the medium temperature region, τ_s increases notably with the increase of treating

Fig.6 Linear relations between $\ln(-\ln\phi)$ and $\ln t$ for flexure and shear at 75 and 97°C

Fig.7 Short-beam shear strengths (a), flexure strengths & modulus (b) at room temperature for CF/PES composites treated for a variety of period at 200°C

Fig.8 Mechanical properties at elevated temperature for CF/PES composites treated at 200°C for 48 hours or 24 hours.

time. For instance, τ_s at 120°C is 64.7MPa for 48 hours treatment and 62.1MPa for 24 hours treatment, respectively, comparing with 57.9MPa for untreated specimen.

CONCLUSION

Water absorption of carbon fiber reinforced polyethersulphone composites obeys Fick's law. The saturation water absorption, M_s , is mainly determined by matrix content. M_s increases rapidly with the increase of temperature in the range examined from 28 to 97°C. Diffusivities obey the relationship $D_c = D_p(1 - a\sqrt{V_f})$. 'a' values obtained from the experimental results at different immersing temperature are nearly identical. Diffusion activation energy decreases with the increase of fiber volume content, which indicates water diffusing in the composites needs relatively small energy.

The mechanical properties of the composites are affected by hygrothermal ageing. The short-beam shear strengths τ_s and flexure strengths σ_f of the composites fall off with prolonging hygrothermal ageing time, but the flexure modulus are hardly affected. The strength reduction of the composites may be described in a function $\phi = \exp(-t^b/\tau)$. The experimental results show the same b exponent for σ_f and τ_s .

A short-time thermal ageing at 200°C has no obvious effects on the mechanical properties of the composites at ambient temperature, but notably enhances the mechanical properties at elevated temperature. So proper post-heat-treatment on the CF/PES composites is useful.

REFERENCES

1. M.S.Woo and M.R.Piggott, *Journal of Composite Technology and Research*, 9(3), 101-107(1987).
2. M.S.Woo and M.R.Piggott, *Journal of Composite Technology and Research*, 9(4), 162-166(1987).
3. D.J.Boll, W.D.Bascom and B.Motiee, *Composites Science and Technology*, 24, 253-273(1985).
4. J.D.Muzzy and A.O.Kays, *Polymer Composites*, 5(3), 169-172(1984).
5. D.J.Willates, *SAMPE Journal*, 20(5), 6-10(1984).
6. A.C.Duthie, *Proc.33rd SAMPE Symposium, Anaheim, 7-10 March*, 296-307(1988).
7. Q.Wang and G.S.Springer, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 23(5), 434-447(1989).
8. C.C.M.Ma and S.W.Hsia, *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 31(1), 34-39(1991).
9. M.Li, Z.W.Wu and X.Y.Tang, *Fuhe Cailiao Xuebao (Chinese)*, 8(2), 63-70(1991).

FIBRES AND MATRICES
